

Supplementary material

Unravelling charge dynamic effects in photocatalytic CO₂ reduction over TiO₂: Anatase vs P25

Laura Collado*, Miguel García-Tecedor, Miguel Gomez-Mendoza, Alejandro Herrero Pizarro, Freddy E. Oropeza, Marta Liras, Víctor A. de la Peña O'Shea*

Photoactivated Processes Unit, IMDEA Energy Institute, Parque Tecnológico de Móstoles, Avda. Ramón de la Sagra 3, 28935 Móstoles, Madrid, Spain.

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Fig. S1. (A) Layout of the gas-phase CO₂ photoreduction reaction system. (B) Emission spectra of the UV lamps used in the photocatalytic tests (four 6W lamps, λ_{\max} =369 nm, average intensity of 47.2Wm⁻²).

Fig. S2. X-ray diffraction profiles of the bare anatase and P25 samples, together with their corresponding diffraction patterns.

Fig. S3. N₂ adsorption-desorption isotherms for anatase and P25 samples.

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Fig. S5. Photoelectron spectra in the cutoff region for P25 with external bias of 5V, measured on three different spots of the sample.

Fig. S6. SEM images of the fabricated samples. (A-C) top-view images of P25 and Anatase samples; (B-D) cross-section images of P25 and Anatase samples.

As it can be observed in Fig. S6, the ITO substrates were covered by a high density of TiO_2 particles. The morphological images show the presence of homogeneous particles with sizes of tens of nm in the case of P25 (Fig. S6A), while in the case of anatase (Fig. S6C), the presence of agglomerates with sizes in the range of few microns were observed. On the other hand, Fig. S6B and Fig. S6D show the cross-section images of P25 and anatase samples, respectively. In both samples a thickness between 600 and 700 nm were observed, even the thickness was slightly higher in the anatase sample due to the presence of bigger agglomerates, as explained above.

Fig. S7. EDX results acquired in the P25 sample.

The chemical composition of the fabricated photoelectrodes was analyzed by terms of Energy Dispersive X-Ray Spectroscopy (EDX), as shown in Fig. S7 and Fig. S8, corresponding to the P25 and anatase samples, respectively. The presence of the expected elements (Si, O, In, Sn and Ti) in the samples under study were confirmed and quantified. As it can be observed in both figures, the Si signal comes from the soda-lime glass, the In signal comes from the ITO transparent electric contact, the Ti comes from the absorber thin-film and the O is present along the whole sample. Notice that the oxygen content includes the corresponding portion of ITO contacts and TiO₂ thin-films.

Fig. S8. EDX results acquired in the Anatase sample.

Fig. S9. Solid-state PL of Anatase and P25 samples ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 300 \text{ nm}$), and schematics of possible recombination pathways (i.e. III - band-to-band recombination; I – recombination between free electrons and hole traps; II – recombination between trapped electrons and VB holes).

Fig. S10. Transient decay traces monitored at 460 nm ($\lambda_{\text{exc}} = 355$ nm) for anatase (red) and P25 (blue) recorded up to 6000 ns after laser pulse (smoothed signal).

Table S1. Accumulated production ($\mu\text{mol g}_{\text{cat}}^{-1}$) in CO_2 photoreduction using H_2O as electron donor for Anatase and P25 after 15 h of reaction under UV light ($\lambda_{\text{max}} = 365 \text{ nm}$).

Catalyst	H₂	CO	CH₄	CH₃OH	C₂H₄	C₂H₆	$\bar{\alpha}$^a	R_{electron}^b
Anatase	78.9	254.8	5.9	9.8	0.0	0.4	0.01	58.4
P25	143.6	283.9	15.3	10.3	0.4	2.0	0.03	125.6

^a $\bar{\alpha}$: Photonic efficiency towards CH_4

^b R_{electron}: represents the rate of electron consumption